

Multidisciplinary design and optimization of H₂-powered regional aircraft architectures

Pablo Norczyk*, Raul Quiben †, Andrea Cini, ‡, Rauno Cavallaro §
Department of Aerospace Engineering, Universidad Carlos III of Madrid, Spain

Hydrogen-powered aircraft offer a promising pathway toward sustainable aviation by significantly reducing pollutant emissions and facilitating scalability for larger aircraft and long-range operations. However, the integration of innovative powerplant components introduces considerable uncertainties in stability and flight system performance, primarily due to the absence of established reference designs. This study utilizes TOPAZ, a novel multidisciplinary design, analysis, and optimization (MDAO) tool based on GEMSEO, to evaluate and optimize three powerplant architectures for regional aircraft: kerosene turboshaft, hydrogen turboshaft, and hydrogen fuel cell systems. The analysis indicates that direct hydrogen combustion can lead to lighter aircraft designs by capitalizing on hydrogen’s high energy density. In contrast, hydrogen fuel cell systems provide enhanced efficiency and reduced hydrogen consumption, albeit with increased takeoff weights. Sensitivity analyses concerning battery-specific energy reveal that hybrid configurations in hydrogen-hybrid architectures yield only marginal hydrogen savings relative to the additional takeoff mass. Consequently, these hybrid systems are most advantageous as power boosters during energy-intensive flight phases, such as climbs.

I. Introduction

AVIATION is currently in the midst of a transformative phase, primarily driven by the urgent need to address and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The sector is working towards achieving a 33% reduction in emissions by 2030 and aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050, as outlined in the 2015 Paris Agreement [1]. This is a significant challenge given that aviation is responsible for approximately 5% of global contribution to global warming. In response, the industry is actively exploring and investing in alternative propulsion technologies that can mitigate its environmental footprint. Hydrogen (H₂) has emerged as a promising alternative fuel, offering a high energy density compared to traditional aviation fuels, while producing zero CO₂ emissions during use. Its capability to power larger aircraft over longer distances, whether through direct combustion or fuel cell systems, positions hydrogen as a viable solution for a diverse range of aviation requirements, outperforming pure battery-electric propulsion systems.

However, adopting hydrogen architectures introduces additional uncertainties and technical challenges, such as managing liquid hydrogen (LH₂) tanks, optimizing the power split between the battery and the fuel cell, or addressing shifts in the center of gravity. These changes lead to complex trade-offs that must be explored. In light of this, multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO) tools for aircraft development have become invaluable assets. These platforms facilitate automated, physics-based decision-making during the early design stages, enabling an extensive exploration of the design spaces relevant to H₂-powered aircraft. By quantitatively assessing different architectural options, MDO tools address the challenges posed by the lack of historical data and established best practices in hydrogen aviation, steering the industry towards more efficient and sustainable solutions. Furthermore, MDO for hydrogen architectures has already demonstrated its effectiveness in optimizing aircraft sizing [2–4]. This paper aims to advance the methodologies of H₂ aircraft MDO by incorporating a geometric-centric approach that ensures all components within the architecture are geometrically feasible, including aircraft architecture decisions within the early stages.

This paper is organized as follows: Initially, the methodology for characterizing the regional airplane architectures will be presented, including a comprehensive description of the models utilized for estimating aircraft performance. Following this, a concise overview of the MDA strategy will be introduced. The MDO problem will be then presented, followed by a review and analysis of the results. Finally a set of conclusions will be provided.

*Researcher, pnorczyk@pa.uc3m.es

†PhD Candidate, rquiben@ing.uc3m.es

‡Visiting Professor, acini@ing.uc3m.es

§Associate Professor, rauno.cavallaro@uc3m.es

II. Methodology

TOPAZ (Tool for Optimizing Powerplants and Aircraft with Zero-emissions) is a Python-written tool built on top of GEMSEO, an open-source library for the development of multidisciplinary optimization problems. TOPAZ, initially based on MOTIVATION tool [2, 5], provides a step forward in terms of modeling power of the aircraft synthesis process by adding several features needed to (1) express the volumetric availability when allocating payload, fuel and/or powertrain systems, and (2) to guide such allocation maintaining target longitudinal stability performances.

The TOPAZ framework leverages on GEMSEO by generating a group of disciplines that define the aircraft characteristics and its performance. For the aircraft definition disciplines, the platform takes a series of classes that, given a set of inputs —such as the power rating of powerplant components or the position of the wing along the fuselage—provide the position, shape, and centers of gravity of every component of the aircraft. Then, a list of performance estimation disciplines takes the previously characterized aircraft and assesses the mission analysis, obtaining all state variables along the mission —such as throttle of powerplant components, fuel consumption rates, and trim angles— in conjunction with variables of interest —such as the balanced field length or total fuel burn—. Given that many of the aircraft state variables are implicit in nature, a Multidisciplinary Design Analysis (MDA) is employed to solve the system.

With the MDA built, a series of design variables, constraints, and an objective are provided to perform the optimization. Once a feasible solution is found, all information is saved, and an OpenVSP model [6] of the aircraft is generated to let the user visualize the result.

TOPAZ requires users to provide a complete parametric description of the aircraft layout. This includes both fixed parameters that remain constant during optimization—such as the cabin cross-section, number of wings, and number of seats—and variables that the optimizer can adjust, such as the position of the wing along the fuselage and wing area. For the powerplant, users must specify the connections between the powerplant components and their respective surrogate models to estimate performance —propeller maps, electric motor maps—. Once these configurations are established, general methods are applied to trim the aircraft and determine the overall mission performance. This object-oriented approach simplifies the process, as users only need to define the aircraft architecture as a collection of objects, which can be reused later on.

The following section will show an example of the definition of a T-tailed regional aircraft architecture with the methods employed to estimate mission performance.

A. Regional Aircraft Parametric Definition

The initial step in defining a regional aircraft parametrically involves selecting the cabin cross-section. Figure 1 illustrates two options: a four-seat layout similar to the DH8C [7] and a five-seat layout similar to A220 [8]. The choice of cabin cross-section affects key parameters, including the required fuselage diameter to support the seating capacity and the area designated for batteries or powerplant systems beneath the passenger cabin. For this paper, the DH8C-like configuration is selected.

Fig. 1 Fuselage and battery layout for DH8C-like aircraft (left) and A220-like aircraft (right).

After selecting the cabin cross-section, the next step involves determining the internal layout by designating specific fuselage sections for various purposes. As shown in Fig.2, the fuselage is divided into several key areas. In this example, the pilot’s cockpit is located at the nose of the aircraft, followed by a luggage compartment —that measures 3.5 meters, similar to that of an ATR72 [9]—. Behind the luggage area is the passenger cabin, which includes a fixed number of seats and a specific seat pitch —in this case, there are 68 seats with a pitch of 0.76 meters—. For architectures that require so, batteries are placed in front and at the rear of the landing gear fairing. For aircraft configurations using liquid hydrogen (LH_2) as fuel, two cryogenic tanks are positioned at the rear to accommodate the additional length required for the tanks. This design choice allows for flexibility in the fuselage length. The dimensions of the cockpit, the passenger cabin, and the tapered fuselage section at the rear are all based on typical aircraft design standards[10, 11] *

Fig. 2 Description of the longitudinal cabin assignment for a DH8C-like aircraft with LH_2 and FC system. The cabin arrangement considers a front luggage compartment, a middle passenger cabin, and a rear-end reserved section for the H_2 tanks.

In the design of aircraft’s wing and tail configuration, the position along the fuselage, the aspect ratio, and the wing area are treated as design variables. For the empennage, the area of the horizontal tail is also a design variable, while the vertical tail is sized similarly to configurations of reference aircraft. This approach allows the optimizer to adjust the wing position and the relationship between the wing and horizontal tail areas in response to changes in the center of gravity during different optimization iterations, thus ensuring the aircraft maintains adequate stability.

For sizing the power plant, the nacelle is adjusted based on the varying volumes of its components. These volumes are determined using specific volume data (L/kW) sourced from existing literature. Besides aiding in the visual representation of the aircraft, these adjustments are essential for estimating mass and calculating parasitic drag. Additionally, the parametric design of the aircraft establishes the necessary information to define the constraints that ensure that kerosene can be stored in the wings and that the hydrogen tanks do not interfere with the cabin space, among other considerations.

B. Weight estimation

After establishing the dimensions and relative positions of the aircraft components, the next step is to estimate their masses. This estimation is carried out using established empirical formulas applicable to aircraft design. The formulas from Raymer’s book [10] are employed for the wing, horizontal and vertical tail surfaces, landing gear, nacelles, and furnishings. The Torenbeek model was employed for the fuselage mass calculation as it yielded more accurate tendencies [11]. Regarding the payload, standard weights for a passenger and their luggage are considered, specifically 75.4 kg and 7.9 kg, respectively [12]. Passengers are assumed to occupy the passenger cabin, while their luggage is stored in the forward section of the aircraft. For the powerplant components, component weights are estimated using specific power values (kg/kW) sourced from the literature. Furthermore, the weights of all components, including additional operating item masses, have been adjusted based on the weight breakdown of the ATR72 from [13].

*Here, we consider the cockpit to be 1.65 times the diameter of the fuselage, while the tapered rear end is 2.7 times the diameter.

Once the masses and dimensions are determined, the center of gravity[†] x_{cg} is calculated using the formula provided in Eq.1.

$$x_{cg} = \frac{\sum m_i \cdot x_{cdg,i} + (m_{fuel} - m_{fuel,burnt}) \cdot x_{cdg,fuel}}{\sum m_i + m_{fuel} - m_{fuel,burnt}} \quad (1)$$

Important considerations are taken for the fuel as its contribution to the CG location is influenced by the total amount of fuel loaded for the mission, which is initially unknown, and the amount burned during flight, which changes throughout the mission. Therefore, the CG position is determined iteratively in conjunction with the aircraft's MDA. This iterative process results in a vector of CG positions along the flight mission.

C. Aerodynamic Modeling

For the aerodynamic model, TOPAZ relies on classic quadratic drag-polar, and linearized lift and moment coefficients. In particular, as also the elevator deflection is considered, 5 drag coefficient, (C_{D_0} , C_{D_α} , $C_{D_{\alpha\alpha}}$, $C_{D_{\delta_e}}$ and $C_{D_{\delta_e\delta_e}}$), 3 lift coefficient, (C_{L_0} , C_{L_α} , and $C_{L_{\delta_e}}$) and 3 pitching moment parameters (C_{M_0} , C_{M_α} and $C_{M_{\delta_e}}$) need to be provided, such that:

$$\begin{cases} C_L = C_{L_0} + \alpha \cdot C_{L_\alpha} + \delta_e \cdot C_{L_{\delta_e}} \\ C_D = C_{D_0} + \alpha \cdot (C_{D_\alpha} + \alpha \cdot C_{D_{\alpha\alpha}}) + \delta_e \cdot (C_{D_{\delta_e}} + \delta_e \cdot C_{D_{\delta_e\delta_e}}) \\ C_M = C_{M_0} + \alpha \cdot C_{M_\alpha} + \delta_e \cdot C_{M_{\delta_e}} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

This method allows the aerodynamic coefficients to be evaluated according to the sought level of fidelity.

This data shows the aerodynamic contribution to the three trim equations in Eq.3, where W is the aircraft mass at the given flight point, γ is the flight path angle, q is the dynamic pressure and S_{ref} the reference surface. These equations are solved to find the required angle of attack α , horizontal tail deflection δ_e , and the required thrust T_{req} .

$$\begin{cases} W \cdot \cos(\gamma) = q \cdot S_{ref} \cdot C_L[\alpha, \delta_e] \\ W \cdot \sin(\gamma) = T_{req} - q \cdot S_{ref} \cdot C_D[\alpha, \delta_e] \\ C_M = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In this paper, the calculation of lift and vortex-induced drag components adheres to the methodology presented in [14]. For the total drag (including takeoff falps and landing gear corrections), handbook formulas from sources such as [10, 11, 15, 16] are applied; notice that the dependence on Mach and Reynolds numbers is maintained. The aerodynamic coefficients change along the mission with the altitude, due to compressibility and Reynolds number effects, and the moment coefficient also changes with the shift of the CG position. Hence, these coefficients are recalculated and converged during each iteration of the MDA.

For the static stability margins, the neutral point (x_{np}) relative to the leading edge is calculated throughout the mission using Equation 4. The w subindices refer to the wing surface, and the HTP refers to the horizontal tail surface, with ε being the downwash.

$$x_{np} = \frac{(x_w + \Delta x_{w,ac}) C_{L\alpha,w} + \frac{S_{HTP}}{S_w} (x_{HTP} + \Delta x_{HTP,ac}) C_{L\alpha,HTP} \left(1 - \frac{d\varepsilon}{d\alpha}\right)}{C_{L\alpha,w} + \frac{S_{HTP}}{S_w} C_{L\alpha,HTP} \left(1 - \frac{d\varepsilon}{d\alpha}\right)} \quad (4)$$

The static margin is determined using Equation 5, with \bar{c}_w being the wing's mean aerodynamic chord. . With the definition of the SM within the MDA, a (vector of) constraint(s) can be easily defined at the optimization level to guarantee a prescribed level of longitudinal static stability along the whole mission.

$$SM = \frac{x_{np} - x_{cg}}{\bar{c}_w} \quad (5)$$

D. Powerplant component modelling

Regarding the powerplant modeling, TOPAZ includes a series of object-oriented surrogate-based models in order to evaluate the powerplant performance. This includes Lithium batteries, turboshafts (for both Kerosene and Hydrogen combustion), fuel cells, cryogenic hydrogen tanks, electric machines, inverters, and propellers.

[†] Referred to the aircraft's nose.

1. Lithium battery

An uncooled 0D simplified battery model is considered for the lithium battery model. The maximum energy storage capacity of the battery is determined by its specific energy, denoted as $\text{SPEC}_{\text{ener}}$, measured in Wh/kg. At full battery (zero depth-of-discharge DoD), the battery’s maximum power output is defined by another parameter, SPEC_{pow} , measured in W/kg. For power levels at higher DoD, a multiplier γ is considered to account for voltage decay out of the battery, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (left). This data is based on a reference Lithium-Ion cell [17]. For the battery technology, C-25 HER battery projections predict specific energy levels of 450 Wh/kg before 2030, and values up to 750 Wh/kg by 2035 [18], with the specific power dependent on the discharge rate C (Tab.1). For the specific battery volume, 500Wh/kg projected batteries are estimated to achieve a volumetric energy density in the orders of 1100 Wh/L [19], leading to a specific volume of 0.41 L/kg.

Fig. 3 Left: Normalized Specific power as a function of the discharge depth. The shaded area represents the out-of-envelope area. Right: electric machine efficiency map as a function of the non-dimensional torque Q/Q_{max} and non-dimensional rpm Ω/Ω_{max} .

C [h^{-1}]	$\text{Spec}_{\text{ener}}$ [Wh/kg]	Spec_{pow} [W/kg]
1	512	500
3	423	1269
5	332	1660
7	284	1988

Table 1 Relationship between specific energy and specific power for IMOTHEP ASS-LA battery [18]. For a given cell technology as the discharge rate C increases, the specific power increases but the specific energy decreases.

2. Electric machine

Two types of electric machines are considered: generators and electric motors. Electric motors provide a specific amount of shaft power based on a given electrical input, while generators convert a certain amount of shaft power into electricity. Energy losses in both cases are represented by an efficiency map, which varies with torque and revolutions. An example of a normalized efficiency map is illustrated in Fig. 3, right. This normalized map indicates that from 0 revolutions to $0.45 \Omega_{max}$ (where Ω_{max} is the motor’s maximum RPM), the electric machine is torque-limited to Q_{max} (the maximum torque). Beyond $0.45 \Omega_{max}$, it becomes power-limited. Given the design variables for the electric machine, i.e., maximum power rating $P_{max,em}$ and maximum revolutions Ω_{max} , the machine must satisfy the following three constraints:

$$\begin{cases} P < P_{max} \\ Q < Q_{max} = \frac{P_{max}}{0.45 \cdot \Omega_{max}} \\ \Omega < \Omega_{max} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Given the efficiency $\eta(Q, \Omega)$ interpolated at the operation point, the consumed electrical power by the electric machine can be expressed as Eq.7 where the δ_t represents the linear throttle of the electric motor. In the case of the generator, the logic inverts. To keep the efficiency map relationships explicit, the electric motor is assumed to be rated to the output shaft power. In contrast, the generator is rated to the output electrical power.

$$P_{in,em} = \frac{P_{out,em}}{\eta(Q, \Omega)} = \frac{P_{max,em} \cdot \delta_t}{\eta(Q, \Omega)} \quad (7)$$

Considering the sizing of the electric machines, current electric motors such as the SP260D provide a specific power of 5.2 kW/kg [20]. However, a specific power of 16 kW/kg will be considered here, according to projections for 2030 operations [21]. The specific volume of the electric machine is based on the specific dimensions of the SP260D adjusted for the projected specific power. Inverters for the electric motor are also considered with a simple loss of efficiency of $\eta_{inv} = 0.98$ and a specific weight of 50 kW/kg for 2030 entry, according to [22]. For low-output electricity generation applications, such as providing power to the cryogenic tank heater, a small generator is assumed to be integrated into the turboshaft engine with a constant efficiency of $\eta = 0.89$.

3. Fuel cell system

For the fuel cell system model, efficiency curves from the literature based on electrochemical losses and auxiliary power demands [23] are considered, as illustrated in Fig.4. The efficiency of this power curve is defined as the ratio between the actual given power by the fuel cell system, and the maximum power that hydrogen could provide at a given mass flow of inlet air \dot{m}_{air} . An additional compressor with a constant efficiency of $\eta_{comp} = 0.85$ is included to ensure a constant pressure at the fuel cell stack. The required work for the compressor is described in Eq.8,

$$P_{comp} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air} \cdot c_p \cdot T_h * \left(1 - \frac{Pr_{SL}}{Pr_h}\right)^{\frac{1-\kappa}{\kappa}}}{\eta_c} \quad (8)$$

where c_p here is the specific heat of air, T_h the temperature at the given altitude, Pr_{SL} the pressure at sea level, Pr_h the pressure at the given altitude, and κ the isentropic coefficient. Consequently, to achieve a designated power output from the assembly, the fuel cell must also account for the additional power the compressor needs, denoted as P_{comp} . This requirement affects the throttle level δ_{FC} and consequently increases the airflow demand \dot{m}_{air} . This relationship necessitates an iterative process to achieve convergence via a sub-MDA within the powerplant module. The overall efficiency of the combined fuel cell and compressor system can be computed using

$$\eta(h) = \frac{P_{max,FC}(h) \cdot \delta_{FC} - \dot{m}_{air} \cdot c_p \cdot T_h * \left(1 - \frac{Pr_{SL}}{Pr_h}\right)^{\frac{1-\kappa}{\kappa}} / \eta_c}{\Lambda_{H2} \cdot \dot{m}_{H2}} \quad (9)$$

where \dot{m}_{H2} is the hydrogen flow and Λ_{H2} the heating value of hydrogen. Eq.9 assumes that the compressor adjusts only the inlet pressure and not the mass flow rate.

As it can be seen in Fig.4 (right), as the altitude increases, there is a slight decrease in peak system efficiency due to the additional compressor work. In the same way, the maximum power that the system can provide decreases with the decrease in atmospheric density. For the specific power of the fuel cell, the framework considers a total system power (stack+aux+compressor) density of 1.6 kW/kg based on projections for 2030 [24, 25].

4. Turbomachinery modelling

In this study, the multi-shaft turboshaft engine model from PyCycle [26] was employed to evaluate the power-specific fuel consumption (PSFC) and state parameters at various stages of the turboshaft engine (T3t, T4t, p3, and p4) under different output power levels, altitudes, and Mach numbers. The engine parameters from PyCycle were kept constant except altitude (set at 25000 ft) and flight Mach number (set at 0.5). To generate a usable engine performance model, it

Fig. 4 Left: stack and system efficiency curves for the fuel cell. Right: efficiency curves considering compressor effect (decrease in peak efficiency η) and altitude change (decrease in peak output power).

was first examined across a full factorial combination of altitudes (0 ft, 12500 ft, and 25000 ft) and Mach numbers (0.01, 0.3, and 0.6), where the variables were gathered as a function of the feasible output power[‡]. Once all the operation points were computed, the variables were fitted as a function of the output power for each altitude and Mach combination. Once all the fitted curves were obtained, a surrogate model with input dimensions altitude, Mach, and output power was implemented.

Fig. 5 Engine stages variables for a Kerosene multi-spool-turboshaft sized at $M=0.6$, $h=25000\text{ft}$ and $W_{shp}=1800$ hp. The lines and curves correspond the fitted responses while the markers correspond to the obtained data.

Fitted stage variables for the Kerosene and Hydrogen turboshafts can be seen in Fig.5 and Fig.6. The Kerosene minimum PSFC is 2.81 times the PSFC of Hydrogen turboshafts, due to Hydrogen's higher energy density. To evaluate the NO_x emissions for both types, the emission index is calculated using Eq.10 [27].

[‡]As PyCycle considers the multi-spool-turboshaft to have two degrees of freedom, output power, and shaft revolutions, a sub-optimizer was employed to find the revolutions that minimized the PSFC at a given power level. This was assumed to be the operational line of the engine.

Fig. 6 Engine stages variables for a Hydrogen multi-spool-turboshaft sized at $M=0.6$, $h=25000\text{ft}$ and $W_{shp}=1800$ hp. The lines and curves correspond the fitted responses while the markers correspond to the obtained data.

$$\text{EINO}_x = 33.2 \cdot \left(\frac{P_3}{432.7} \right)^{0.4} \cdot \exp \left(\frac{T_3 - 459.67 - 1027.6}{349.9} + \frac{6.29 - 6.3}{53.2} \right) \quad (10)$$

5. Hydrogen tank modelling

For the hydrogen tank, the model considers a homogeneous cryogenic LH_2 based on [28]. The model computes the pressure change rate in the homogeneous tank given the total mass flow leaving the tank \dot{m} and the total heat entering the tank Q . Heat is assumed to enter the tank from outside the tank Q_{out} due to the conduction heat transfer between the inside tank wall and the outside tank wall[§]. A heater and a venting valve are installed to control the tank's internal pressure. When mass flow rates (\dot{m}) are high, the pressure within the tank decreases, necessitating additional heating to increase the pressure partially. Conversely, when mass flow rates are low or negligible, the continuous heat transfer causes the pressure to rise, which may require safety venting to alleviate this pressure increase.

During the optimization process, the heater's heating power (Q_{HX}) and the vented mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{vented}) are treated as design variables to let the optimizer choose the appropriate balance between maintaining pressure, managing heater electricity demand, and regulating the necessary vented mass. These design variables are established at the beginning and end of each flight phase, with intermediate values interpolated linearly across the phase nodes.

6. Propeller model

A propeller model at ATR72-like conditions was generated using XROTOR [29] based on thrust values from BADA. Once the geometry was generated, a J (advance ratio) vs C_P (power coefficient) BEMT-based map was generated. To make the propeller map MDO-ready, the stalled region was filled with constant efficiency value, and the propeller map was smoothed to prevent abrupt changes in the derivatives that could introduce hard non-linearities. Once the data was treated, a surrogate model was constructed to interpolate the propeller efficiency η_{prop} . For the static and very low axial speed conditions, a momentum theory based C_T/C_P vs C_P curve was described [30] and later adjusted using well-known performance estimation curves from [31]. The objective of the static propeller curve is to, given an input C_P , enforce the maximum C_T during takeoff and landing phases.

[§]To reduce the heat entering the tank, an insulation layer t_{insu} with an insulator of thermal conductivity k_{insu} is installed

Fig. 7 Description of the homogeneous hydrogen cryogenic tank model. Heat is introduced into the control volume via conductive heating or active heating, and hydrogen is consumed via venting or consumption by the fuel cells.

Fig. 8 Left: propeller map as a function of C_P and J for the reference propeller design. Right: adjusted static thrust curves for a six-bladed propeller.

7. Powerplant architectures

Three different configurations are proposed in this work: a **twin kerosene turboshaft** configuration, a **twin hydrogen turboshaft** configuration with cryogenic fuel tanks, and a **twin fuel-cell** configuration also utilizing cryogenic fuel tanks.

- The **twin kerosene turboshaft** configuration (Fig. 9, top) features two turboshaft engines powered directly by kerosene. In steady flight, the engines adjust their power output to meet the propeller's power requirements, such that the combined thrust matches the total thrust needed to maintain the aircraft in steady-flight conditions. To make sure that the turboshaft is properly sized, i.e., can provide sufficient power across the mission, a constraint is imposed over the gas turbine throttle δ_{gt} , which is defined as the power needed by the propeller $P_{in,prop}$ divided by the maximum power that the turboshaft can provide at a given altitude h and Mach number M .

$$\delta_{gt} = \frac{P_{in,prop}}{P_{max,h,M}} \quad (11)$$

During the steady flight mission, this throttle must remain below a maximum continuous power of 90% ($\delta_{gt} < 0.9$). For takeoff and landing phases, the throttle is fixed at 0.9 for all-engine-operating (AEO) conditions, and at 1 for one-engine-inoperative (OEI) conditions, with the power generated by the turbo-shaft directly applied to the propeller[¶].

[¶]In this case the thrust is then computed using the propeller maps from Sec.II.D.6.

In addition to the turboshaft throttle, the architecture is constrained to carry all the kerosene at the wings, which in this case has fuel tanks spanning from the leading edge to 0.6 times the mean aerodynamic chord \bar{c} .

Fig. 9 Top: twin turboprop-kerosene architecture. Middle: twin turboprop-hydrogen architecture. Bottom: twin fuel cell hydrogen architecture. Left: OpenVSP model of each architecture powerplant spatial powerplant arrangement. Right: representation for the connection across powerplant components. For all architecture diagrams the power-flow logic is presented for the steady flight phases (left), and takeoff phases (right).

- The **twin hydrogen turboshaft** configuration (see Fig. 9, middle) resembles the kerosene configuration, with the addition of a cryogenic liquid hydrogen (LH₂) tank located at the rear of the fuselage. To power the heating element within the cryogenic tank (P_{HX}), an electric battery is utilized, which can be recharged by a lightweight generator mounted on the turboshaft. This generator is designed solely for recharging the battery and is not responsible for powering other electric propulsion components, such as distributed electric propulsion (DEP).

To manage the battery recharge power, a split factor SF is defined as in Eq. 12. This factor is controlled by specifying its value at the beginning and end of each flight phase, with the intermediate values across the phase nodes being linearly interpolated across the phase^{||}.

$$SF = \frac{\delta_{gt} \cdot P_{max,h,M}}{P_{in,prop}} - 1 \quad (12)$$

In addition to the gas turbine throttle constraint, which is set at $\delta_{gt} = 0.9$ to ensure consistency during both takeoff and landing phases, the multidisciplinary optimization (MDO) must also account for several key requirements regarding battery management. First, the battery's state of charge (SOC) must remain within the operational range of $0.2 < SOC < 1$. Additionally, the power flowing in or out of the battery should not exceed the maximum allowable power based on its current state of charge. This can be expressed as:

$$|P_{in/out,batt}| < W_{batt} \cdot SPEC_{pow,batt} \cdot \Upsilon(DOD) \quad (13)$$

Moreover, fuel tank constraints are added to ensure that the fuel tanks do not overlap with the passenger cabin and that by the end of the extended mission, the hydrogen tank must retain a reserve volume of at least 10% of its total capacity.

- For the **twin fuel-cell** configuration (Fig. 9, bottom), the turboshaft connected to the propeller is replaced with an electric motor with variable shaft revolutions Ω^{**} and a maximum power rating $P_{EM,max}$. The throttle constraint in the gas turbine is now substituted by a throttle in the electric motor, such that during steady flight phases the throttle must satisfy the Eq.14; the logic regarding the fixed throttles of 0.9 during AEO takeoff phases and 1.0 during OEI phases is still applied here. Additional constraints are also enforced on the torque Eq.6.

$$\delta_{EM} = \begin{cases} P_{in,prop}/P_{EM,max} < 0.9, & \text{if AEO} \\ P_{in,prop}/P_{EM,max} < 1.0, & \text{if OEI} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

A battery and a fuel cell system, which includes a compressor, are integrated to supply electric power to the electric motor. To manage the balance between the electricity generated by the fuel cell and the power provided by the battery, a hybridization parameter, HF is defined. The power contributions from the fuel cell and the battery can be expressed in accordance with Equations 15 and 16, respectively.

$$P_{out,batt_side} = HF \cdot P_{in,inv} \quad (15)$$

$$P_{out,FC} = (1 - HF) \cdot P_{in,inv} \quad (16)$$

The total power provided by the battery, denoted as $P_{out,batt}$, is defined in Eq.17. In this context, $P_{out,batt_side}$ represents the electric power along the line connecting each side of the hybrid split to the battery. It's important to note that the power line feeding the heater is connected to the same bus as the lines leading to the hybrid split. Consequently, when the hybrid factor HF takes negative values, the battery can be recharged, provided that the overall electric power at the bus is negative.

$$P_{out,batt} = 2 \cdot P_{out,batt_side} + P_{HX} \quad (17)$$

Two additional constraints are added to ensure that both the fuel cell and the inverters are properly sized (as shown in Eq. 18). For the fuel cell, the power output takes into account losses from the compressor, and its maximum power output varies based on flight altitude.

$$\begin{cases} P_{out,inv}/P_{inv,max} < 0.9, & \text{if AEO} \\ P_{out,inv}/P_{inv,max} < 1.0, & \text{if OEI} \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} P_{out,FC}/P_{FC,max}[h] < 0.9, & \text{if AEO} \\ P_{out,FC}/P_{FC,max}[h] < 1.0, & \text{if OEI} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

^{||}This method is also applied for heating and venting inside the hydrogen tank.

^{**}The RPMs in the electric motor are defined referenced to the tip Mach number to keep the design feasible with large changes in propeller diameter. The value across the mission is once more defined by two design variables, one at the start and one at the end of the phase, with intermediate values being linearly interpolated.

III. Multidisciplinary Analysis

Once all the models and disciplines are defined, the MDA can be defined. Within TOPAZ, the MDA is split between an initial geometry-pre-processing that calculates the distances, masses, and centers of gravity of all the aircraft components. Then, the MDA performs a takeoff analysis, calculates the takeoff performance and balanced takeoff field length, and analyzes the steady flight phases. Finally, the objective and the mass margins are evaluated. This MDA analysis can be visualized in Fig.10.

Fig. 10 N2 diagram for the reference MDA obtained from GEMSEO. Disciplines in orange show the geometry-pre-processing disciplines. Disciplines in green show the takeoff phases. Disciplines in red correspond to the mission steady flight phases. Disciplines in purple show final objective and constraint analysis disciplines.

A. Balanced field length analysis

The balanced field length analysis aims to obtain the decision distance $V1$ and its associated balanced takeoff field length, defined as the distance where the aborted and the accelerated-go distances become equal.

Fig. 11 Example of the balanced takeoff field length speed diagram. The final distances for continued takeoff and aborted takeoff are equal.

In the following implementation, four phases are considered: an initial acceleration $V0V1$ phase with AEO, that goes from $V0$ to $V1$; an acceleration $V1VR$ phase with OEI, that goes from $V1$ to $VR = 1.1V_{stall}$; a rotation phase $VRV2$ with OEI, that goes linearly in speed from VR to $V2 = 1.2V_{stall}$, and goes in altitude from 0ft to clearing an

obstacle of 35ft; and finally finally a deceleration phase $V1V0$, that goes from $V1$ to $V0$. An example of the velocities evolution across a calculated balanced takeoff can be seen in Fig.11.

To conduct this analysis, the MDA shown in Figure 12 is employed. The first step involves calculating the aerodynamic coefficients and the position of the center of gravity. Here, it is assumed that the consumed fuel mass is so little that it can be ignored^{††}, and thus, the center of gravity and the aircraft mass are kept constant. Changes in the aerodynamic coefficients are also considered negligible, with only additional corrections to the clean polar to consider the effects of the flaps and landing gear deployment. Once the aerodynamic coefficients for all phases are found, the next step relies on computing the mechanical power^{‡‡} produced by either the electric motor or the turboshaft, for either case already fixed in throttle for the takeoff phases, and transmitted into the propeller (P_{prop}); this power is employed to calculate, through the propeller map, the produced propeller thrust (T_{prop}).

Fig. 12 MDA for the analysis of the takeoff segments.

With the thrust determined, the horizontal balance of forces (as outlined in Equation 19) can be utilized to calculate the acceleration during the ground roll phases: $V0V1$, $V1VR$, and $V1V0$. To compute the coefficient of drag, the angle of attack (α) that yields a takeoff run coefficient of lift of $CL = 0.2$ has to be found. A $\mu = 0.02$ friction coefficient for the initial acceleration phase and $\mu = 0.2$ during the braking phase is assumed. For the rotation phase, which spans from VR to $V2$, it is assumed that the velocity increases linearly from $1.1V_{stall}$ to $1.2V_{stall}$. Given the maximum coefficient of lift (CL_{max}) of the aircraft, the flight path angle (γ) can be computed using the excess thrust, as described in Eq.3 and Eq.20. Note that in this calculation, the trim of the empennage is also considered to ensure that the pitching moment remains zero.

$$accel = \frac{T_{props} - \mu \cdot N - q \cdot S_{ref} \cdot CD}{MTOW} \quad (19)$$

$$\sin\gamma = \frac{T - D}{W} \quad (20)$$

Once the initial guesses for the accelerations $accel$ during the ground roll phases and the climb angle γ are established, the equations of motion must be integrated. This integration is performed using the discipline `KinematicsIntegrators`, which functions similarly to the MDA illustrated in Fig.13. In this setup, a top-level solver is responsible for adjusting the $V1$ value so that the total horizontal distance covered by $V0V1$, $V1VR$, and $VRV2$ matches the distance covered by $V0V1$ and $V1V0$. Nested within this top-level solver are several inner solvers that take the initial velocities and modify the time increments Δt for each node throughout the phase. The goal is to ensure that the integrated end velocity aligns with the target end velocity for that phase. During the rotation phase, Δt is specifically adjusted to ensure that the final altitude meets the necessary obstacle avoidance altitude.

^{††}Fuel consumption during the takeoff is still tracked and later integrated to determine the weight at the beginning of the climb phase

^{‡‡}For all phases except the braking $V1V0$ phase, where the powerplant does not produce power.

Fig. 13 Inner nested solvers for the $V1$ finding algorithm and the integration of the takeoff segments.

With the vector of times for each phase determined, and the decision distance $V1$ computed, the calculated velocities can be fed back into the propeller and aerodynamic models to calculate the new propeller thrust $T_{prop,new}$, update the vector of accelerations $accel_{new}$, and recalculate the Balanced Flight Length (BFL). This process is managed by the MDA until a convergence criterion is satisfied for the vector of velocities. It's important to note that the nested solvers used to calculate $V1$ and the BFL distance operate independently from the main MDA. This independence is advantageous because it allows for the numerous iterations needed to determine $V1$ and the time increment Δt without being affected by the computationally intensive evaluations of the powerplant and aerodynamic models handled by the MDA.

B. Steady flight phases

Fig. 14 Simplified conceptual MDA for the MDA process during a mission phase segment.

A process similar to the takeoff is followed during the steady flight phases. Initially, the aerodynamic coefficients based on the current flight conditions^{§§} are computed. With the aerodynamic coefficients the trim equations are solved, providing the required angle of attack (α), the elevator deflection (δ_e) and required thrust (T_{req}). During this stage the static margin is also determined.

After calculating the required thrust, a solver determines the necessary propeller power to produce the required thrust based on the propeller performance map. Once the required shaft power is obtained, this information is fed as an

^{§§}The current mission flight conditions are computed a priori, based on the mission profile by integrating the horizontal and vertical velocities, taking into account the altitudes, mission distances, and holding times

input to the powerplant architectures. These architectures provide various outputs, including the fuel mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{fuel,H_2}), the rate of the battery state of charge (\dot{SOC}), and the rate of change in tank pressure (p_{tank,LH_2}); next to other outputs such as constraints and other state variables of interest. The rates are also integrated in order to obtain the state of charge of the battery and hydrogen fuel tanks, as well as to obtain the consumed fuel (kerosene or hydrogen) mass. This mass is subtracted from the MTOW to determine the current aircraft mass, which is fed back to the equations of trim (as now the aircraft mass is smaller), and to the center of gravity calculation discipline, that obtains the new x_{cdg} fed back to the aerodynamic coefficients discipline that updates the aerodynamic coefficients.

State variables are passed at the end of one phase to the start of the new phase and the whole feed-back loop is converged with the MDA.

C. Optimization function and margins

Once the mission is flown, the objective function has to be evaluated. For this framework, the cost function considered is the one in Eq.21, where the consumed fuel weight can be specified for either optimization of the nominal mission (climb-cruise-descent) or the extended mission (including diversion mission and holding). In addition, another objective is to minimize the mass of the aircraft for operative reasons; this is weighted to obtain a good tradeoff. A multiplier ϱ is included here to consider the change in fuel type^{¶¶} and thus to maintain the weighting with the *MTOW*.

$$\Theta = \frac{W_{fuel,final}}{W_{PL}} \cdot \varrho + \frac{MTOW}{16000} \quad (21)$$

In addition to this, the MDA has to consider consistency in *MTOW*, this is done by summing the weight of all the components of the aircraft plus the fuel burnt and ensuring that:

$$MTOW > \sum m_{i,aircraft} + W_{PL} + W_{fuel} \quad (22)$$

For the case of hydrogen-based architectures, the fuel weight is omitted if the component mass of the hydrogen tank considers its weight with the tanks filled, leading to the constraint of the *SOC* of the tank to ensure that there is sufficient volume of hydrogen for the mission.

IV. Case Study

For this paper, the three regional aircraft architectures from Fig.9 are considered, and for the flight profile, the mission from Fig.15 is considered. It involves a standard mission distance of 1,200 nautical miles, including a diversion to a secondary airport located 300 miles away and a 30-minute holding phase. The aircraft maintains a steady equivalent airspeed of 195 knots throughout the mission, corresponding to a cruise Mach number of 0.417. Design specifications for all three architectures are detailed in Table 2, while relevant constraints are outlined in Table 3. Equation 21 specifies the objective function used in this analysis.

To control weight, the maximum takeoff weight (*MTOW*) for all three architectures is capped at 30 tons. This limitation aims to restrict the overall weight increase to no more than 30% compared to similar aircraft, such as the ATR72, which share the same seating capacity and mission profile.

Two studies are considered:

- **Study 1** compares directly the three different architectures: *Architecture 1: Twin Kerosene Turboshaft*, *Architecture 2: Twin Hydrogen Turboshaft*, and *Architecture 3: Twin Hydrogen Fuel Cell*. For both the hydrogen architectures, we assume a battery-specific energy of 45 Wh/kg and a gravimetric efficiency of $\eta_{grav} = 0.65$. This specific energy is chosen so that in the serial architecture (fuel cell), the battery is sized only for the thermal management of the fuel tank. This approach ensures that most energy comes from the liquid hydrogen itself, allowing for a fair and direct comparison between the architectures.
- **Study 2** focuses on the impact of battery-specific energy within *Architecture 3*. The goal here is to evaluate how hybridization can optimize the sizing of the fuel-cell powerplant system.

^{¶¶}For the case of hydrogen $\varrho = 2.87$

Regional aircraft reference trajectory

Fig. 15 Flight altitudes, match number, and flight path angle γ for a reference regional aircraft mission with both nominal and extended flight phases.

Design Variable (Units)	Kerosene turboshaft		Hydrogen turboshaft		Hydrogen Fuel Cell	
	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
Prop Diameter (m)	0.1	5	0.1	5	0.1	5
Prop Tip Mach (-)	0.1	0.9	0.1	0.9	—	—
Wing AR (-)	5	40	6	35	6	30
Wing Surface (m ²)	20	200	20	200	20	200
N-d wing position (-)	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.8
HTP surface (m ²)	1	20	1	20	1	20
Fuselage length (m)	33	40	33	40	33	40
MTOW (kg)	5000	30000	5000	30000	5000	30000
W_{PL} (kg)	5664.4	5773.2	5664.4	5773.2	5664.4	5773.2
Turboshaft Rating (kW)	6.7	37000	6.7	37000	—	—
Fuel cell Rating (kW)	—	—	—	—	6.7	37000
Electric motor Rating (kW)	—	—	—	—	6.7	37000
Inverter Rating (kW)	—	—	—	—	6.7	37000
Battery weight (kg)	—	—	50	5000	50	5000
Filled LH ₂ tank weight (kg)	—	—	50	5000	50	5000
LH ₂ tank insulation (m)	—	—	0.0001	0.6	0.0001	0.6
HF_{start}	—	—	—	—	-1	1
HF_{end}	—	—	—	—	-1	1
$M_{prop,start}$	—	—	—	—	0.1	0.9
$M_{prop,end}$	—	—	—	—	0.1	0.9
SF_{start}	—	—	-1	0	—	—
SF_{end}	—	—	-1	0	—	—
$\dot{m}_{venting,start}$ (kg/s)	—	—	0	1	0	1
$\dot{m}_{venting,end}$ (kg/s)	—	—	0	1	0	1
$P_{HX,start}$ (kW)	—	—	0	60	0	60
$P_{HX,end}$ (kW)	—	—	0	60	0	60

Table 2 Design variables and bounds for Kerosene, Hydrogen, and Fuel Cell architectures. Values in **red** indicate that the following design variable does not apply to the architecture and is thus not included in the architecture's MDO. The values shown in **green** are applied to all the phases.

Constraint (Units)	Kerosene turboshaft		Hydrogen turboshaft		Hydrogen Fuel Cell	
	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
Turboshaft Throttle (-)	-	0.9	-	0.9	—	—
Fuel cell Throttle (-)	—	—	—	—	-	0.9
Electric motor Throttle (-)	—	—	—	—	-	0.9
MTOW margin (kg)	0.01	-	0.01	-	0.01	-
Fuselage cabin clearance (m)	0.01	-	0.01	-	0.01	-
BFL (m)	-	1500	-	1500	-	1500
Static Margin	0.2	-	0.2	-	0.2	-
$C_{P,prop}$	-	0.9	-	0.9	-	0.9
Vol LH ₂ tank (m ³)	—	—	$1.05V_{H2,used}$	-	$1.05V_{H2,used}$	-
Press LH ₂ tank	—	—	P_{atm}	$3 \cdot P_{atm}$	P_{atm}	$3 \cdot P_{atm}$
SOC_{batt} (-)	0.2	1	0.2	1	0.2	1
Battery $P_{out,batt}$ (kW)	$-P_{max,batt}$	$P_{max,batt}$	$-P_{max,batt}$	$P_{max,batt}$	$-P_{max,batt}$	$P_{max,batt}$

Table 3 Constraints upper and lower margins for the Kerosene, Hydrogen, and Fuel Cell architectures. Values in red indicate that the following design variable does not apply to the architecture and is thus not included in the architecture’s MDO. The values indicated in blue correspond to constraints for each point along a phase, applied to all the phases.

V. Results

The results of **Study 1** are presented in Tab.4; as it can be seen, the direct burn of hydrogen leads to a 6.18% decrease in MTOW as the fuel goes from 2261.65 kg of Kerosene to 825.627 kg of LH₂ in a 444.57 kg cryogenic tank, leading to an overall decrease in powerplant weight. This decrease in required fuel mass is to be expected, given the higher energy density of hydrogen, which can also be seen in the total emissions of NO_x, where a 62.81% reduction of total emissions is seen. The rate of emissions along the mission can be observed in Fig.16 where, for similar throttle levels, the direct combustion of hydrogen leads to lower NO_x emissions.

When comparing now the hydrogen-based architectures, the fuel cell system reveals a 14.47% reduction in required LH₂ compared to the turboshaft architecture, thanks to the greater efficiency of hydrogen fuel cells versus direct combustion in turboshafts. However, it’s important to note that the fuel cell system is heavier, resulting in a 7.17% increase in MTOW. The total powerplant mass increases from 1216.44 kg (for the two kerosene turboshafts), to 3522.22 kg (including fuel cells, electric motors, and inverters), marking a significant 189.55% increase in powerplant mass. This means that while the fuel cell system is more efficient in terms of total LH₂ needed; it is also heavier than both the hydrogen turboshaft architecture and the kerosene turboshaft architecture.

Fig. 16 Left: Comparison of the NO_x emissions for the Kerosene and Hydrogen based turboshafts. Right: corresponding throttle level. The larger decrease in throttle level for the Kerosene architecture is due to the larger decrease in overall aircraft mass due to fuel consumption.

Variable (Units)	Kerosene turboshaft	Hydrogen turboshaft	Hydrogen Fuel Cell
Prop Diameter (m)	2.940	3.067	2.804
Prop Tip Mach (-)	0.704	0.688	—
Wing AR (-)	16.318	16.481	16.215
Wing Surface (m ²)	62.296	64.281	64.263
N-d wing position (-)	0.449	0.458	0.452
HTP surface (m ²)	9.189	9.70	10.1324
Fuselage length (m)	33.15	35.11	34.42
MTOW (kg)	22637.9	21438.7	24261.7
W_{PL} (kg)	5773.2	5773.2	5773.2
Turboshaft Rating (kW)	2213.35	2195.58	—
Fuel cell Rating (kW)	—	—	2599.71
Electric motor Rating (kW)	—	—	1600.11
Inverter Rating (kW)	—	—	1814.37
Battery weight (kg)	—	200	200
Filled LH ₂ tank weight (kg)	—	1270.2	1086.66
LH ₂ tank insulation (m)	—	0.0730	0.00413
Balanced Field Length (m)	968.73	1118.24	1499.97
Fuel consumed (kg)	2264.23	825.993	706.429
Total NO _x emitted (kg)	49.455	18.39	0
Wing mass (kg)	2842.7	2795.08	3041.94
Empenage mass (kg)	457.023	466.95	482.554
Fuselage and furnishing mass (kg)	6448.73	6249.2	6221.24
Avionics and subsystems (kg)	2500.85	2500.85	2500.85
Landing gear mass (kg)	724.265	700.187	770.656
Nacelles mass (kg)	435.91	433.196	659.046
Turboshafts mass (kg)	1216.44	1208.512	—
Fuel cells mass (kg)	—	—	3249.64
Inverters mass (kg)	—	—	72.5748
Electric motors mass (kg)	—	—	200.01

Table 4 Results from case study 1. Design variables and state variables of interest are shown.

From a design perspective, to transition from a kerosene turboshaft to a hydrogen turboshaft, the fuselage length must increase by 5.91% to accommodate liquid hydrogen (LH₂) tanks. This change also requires a slight adjustment in the wings' position, moving them further back on the fuselage to balance the added weight at the rear, with the non-dimensional wing position shifting from 0.449 to 0.458. On the other hand, when using a fuel cell system, the increase in fuselage length is only 3.83%, as the hydrogen tanks are smaller. A comparison of the three optimized design architectures can be found in Fig.17.

Regarding balance, all architectures experience a shift in their center of gravity, as illustrated in Figure 18 (top left). For the Kerosene architecture, this shift occurs backward because the fuel tanks are positioned at the leading edge of the wings, which is in front of the center of gravity (cog). As a result, the minimum static margin is observed during landing (Figure 18, top right). In contrast, hydrogen architectures experience a forward shift since their fuel tanks are located in the rear fuselage, behind the cog. This leads to the minimum static margin occurring during takeoff and the initial climb. Examining the angle of attack, α (Figure 18, bottom left), we can see that the Kerosene architecture exhibits a more significant decrease in α during cruise segments due to the greater mass loss. However, when analyzing the ratio between the tail trim angle, δ_e , and the angle of attack, α , we find that the necessary gain in the tail trim angle increases considerably. This can lead to an increase of up to 33.32% in the δ_e/α ratio, even when accounting for larger horizontal stabilizer areas (Table 4) and longer lever arms. This underlines the importance of conducting a thorough balance analysis when considering new architectures that may deviate from the standard volume ratios found in existing literature.

Fig. 17 Resulting baseline aircraft configurations for the three aircraft powerplant configurations.

Fig. 18 Top left: non-dimensional position of the center of gravity along the fuselage. Top right: static margin. Bottom left: angle of attack α needed to trim the aircraft. Bottom right: the ratio between empennage trim angle δ_e and α .

Examining the pressure management system in the hydrogen tank (see Fig.19), it can be seen that the control system implemented can properly handle as design variables the heating and the venting to allow the tank to operate within the operative limits. Notably, the system predominantly uses heating to maintain pressure, with minimal hydrogen venting, only during the extended mission phase of the fuel cell architecture. It is important to approach the results from this section with caution, as the simplicity of the thermodynamic model used (which assumes a homogeneous monophasic) may lead to results that differ from those obtained using more complex thermodynamic models.

Fig. 19 Top left: Pressure inside the hydrogen tank, areas in red indicate tank operational limits. Top right: heater power across the mission. Lower left: hydrogen consumption along the mission. Lower right: ventilated hydrogen along the mission.

Regarding the **Study 2**, it can be seen in Fig.20 that as the specific energy increases, the LH₂ fuel consumed across the whole mission (reference and extended) decreases. However, two tendencies can be observed here: in the first tendency — specific energy between 45 Wh/kg and 125 Wh/kg— the batteries inside the fuselage grow until they are able to occupy the whole space inside the cabin. During this stage the power rating of the fuel cell also decreases (Fig.21, right), showing that the battery power is initially being employed to act as a *power booster* during climb, reducing the power rating requirement of the fuel cell system. Here, therefore, a noticeable trend can be observed: with increasing specific energy, the power rating of the fuel cell decreases, reducing the powertrain (omitting the batteries) mass, leading to slightly more mass for the batteries at a given MTOW. This trend persists until the battery volume constraints are reached leading to an upper bound on the battery mass, as it can be inferred from Fig.21 (left). Once the battery weight is constrained due to the limited cabin volume (specific energies from 125 Wh/kg upwards) an increase in the specific energy of the battery leads to a decrease in the aircraft MTOW due to the reduction in the required LH₂.

Looking at the hybridization profiles along the mission (Fig.22, upper left) the aforementioned behavior can be verified, as for lower specific energy values, hybridization is increased at the nominal climb segment to reduce the peak of throttle at the fuel cell (Fig. 22, upper right), leading to the fuel cell to be sized for the nominal cruise. However, it can also be noticed that once this is achieved, the hybridization tends to increase more during the cruise phase, operating the fuel cell at lower throttle levels during the mission. This is to be expected as looking at the fuel cell efficiency tendencies Fig.4, the fuel cell operates at a higher efficiency at lower throttle levels, therefore instead of keeping with the under-sizing of the fuel cell, the fuel cell is now operated at lower throttle levels, with the sizing point now being the climb of the diversion segment where the aircraft is operating mostly out of the LH₂ and the batteries are discharged.

Fig. 20 LH₂ fuel used as a function of the specific energy for the hydrogen serial hybrid architecture.

Fig. 21 Top left: Evolution of the battery mass as a function of the specific energy. Top right: evolution of the fuel cell rating as a function of the specific energy. Bottom: evolution of the MTOW as a function of the specific energy.

Fig. 22 Top left: Evolution of the hybridization along the mission. Top right: evolution of the fuel cell throttle along the mission. Bottom left: evolution of the state of charge along the mission. Bottom right: evolution of the hydrogen flow along the mission.

The results indicate that, as increasing battery specific energy, the optimal configurations for hybrid fuel cell architectures require less hydrogen and lower fuel cell ratings, but result in a significantly higher maximum takeoff weight (MTOW).

When comparing the optimized fuel cell aircraft with an energy density of 45 Wh/kg to direct hydrogen combustion, there is a reduction of 17.67% in hydrogen requirements, albeit with a 13.16% increase in MTOW. For the fuel cell aircraft with an energy density of 425 Wh/kg, the hydrogen requirement decreases by 29.57%, but the MTOW increases by 28.13%. Finally, when comparing the 425 Wh/kg configuration to the 45 Wh/kg setup, there is a 17.68% reduction in hydrogen requirements alongside a 22.95% increase in MTOW.

These findings suggest that the primary advantage of the hybrid-electric fuel cell architecture lies in the fuel cell's superior efficiency. In contrast, adding more batteries, even with higher specific energies, yields only a modest reduction in hydrogen consumption, while significantly increasing the Maximum Takeoff Weight (MTOW)

This is due to hydrogen's high energy density, where the percentage decrease in fuel requirements does not lead to significant reductions in aircraft mass that could accommodate more batteries, a scenario more likely in kerosene-based hybrid architecture

VI. Conclusion

This paper has demonstrated the application of the novel GEMSEO-based framework, TOPAZ, in the multidisciplinary design, sizing, and optimization of regional hydrogen-based aircraft architectures. The findings reveal that direct hydrogen combustion results in lighter aircraft due to hydrogen's higher energy density compared to kerosene, while fuel cell-powered aircraft are more efficient and consume less hydrogen but require higher maximum takeoff weights. The integration of full geometrical aspects, including parametric intersection constraints and mass balancing, underscores the importance of addressing these factors early in the design process, as novel configurations may impose greater stability and tail design requirements. Lastly, a sensitivity analysis of specific energy indicates that in hydrogen-hybrid architectures, hydrogen's high energy density only marginally reduces fuel requirements compared to the significant increases in maximum takeoff mass.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization and Methodology: Norczyk, Cavallaro. Software Development: Norczyk Investigation: MDO: Norczyk and Cavallaro (MDO), Norczyk, Quiben and Cini (Systems). Writing: Norczyk, Quiben, Cavallaro. Supervision & Funding Acquisition: A. Cini and R. Cavallaro.

Acknowledgments

The research work is carried out as part of the research project OPERATIONAL (TED2021-131119A-I00), funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

References

- [1] Agreement, P., “Paris Agreement,” Report of the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (21st Session, 2015: Paris), 2015. Retrieved December, Vol. 4, HeinOnline, 2015, p. 2017.
- [2] Figueroa, R. Q., Cavallaro, R., Cini, A., and Arnedo, M. S., “MOTIVATION (Mdao fOr susTaInable aViATION) - Framework development for the design and optimization of H2 powered aircraft,” *AIAA AVIATION 2023 Forum*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2023-4151>.
- [3] Adler, E. J., and Martins, J. R. R. A., “Blended wing body configuration for hydrogen-powered aviation,” *AIAA Aviation 2023 Forum*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2023-4020>.
- [4] Proesmans, P., and Vos, R., “Hydrogen, medium-range airplane design optimization for minimal global warming impact,” *CEAS Aeronautical Journal*, Vol. 15, No. 4, 2024, pp. 781–806. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13272-024-00734-w>.
- [5] Quiben Figueroa, R., Cavallaro, R., and Cini, A., “Feasibility studies on regional aircraft retrofitted with hybrid-electric powertrains,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 151, 2024, p. 109246. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2024.109246>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1270963824003778>.
- [6] McDonald, R. A., and Gloude-mans, J. R., “Open Vehicle Sketch Pad: An Open Source Parametric Geometry and Analysis Tool for Conceptual Aircraft Design,” *AIAA SCITECH 2022 Forum*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2022-0004>, aIAA 2022-0004, Preprint.
- [7] Bombardier Inc., *Airport Planning Manual: Series 100, PSM 1-81-13*, Bombardier Aerospace Regional Aircraft, Airline Services, 123 Garratt Blvd., Downsview, Ontario, Canada M3K 1Y5, 1999. Copyright © 1999 by Bombardier Inc. All rights reserved.
- [8] Airbus Canada Limited Partnership, *Aircraft Characteristics Publication (ACP) A322*, Airbus Canada Limited Partnership, Customer Services, 13100 Henri-Fabre Blvd., Mirabel, Quebec, Canada J7N 3C6, 2024.
- [9] ATR, *ATR72 Flight Crew Operating Manual*, July 1999. Flight Crew Operating Manual.
- [10] Raymer, D. P., *Aircraft design: A conceptual approach*, AIAA education series, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Va., 2006.
- [11] Torenbeek, E., *Synthesis of Subsonic Airplane Design*, Delft University Press, Delft, 1988.
- [12] Berg, H., Macedo, P., Picinatti, B., Adler, M., Pel, S., and Jacobs, K., “Review of Standard Passenger Weights: Final Report,” Tech. rep., Lufthansa Consulting GmbH and SEO Amsterdam Economics, Frankfurt/M., Germany, September 2022. Report submitted to the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) under Contract Reference EASA.2021.C24.
- [13] Attanasio, L., De Marco, A., Nicolosi, F., and Vecchia, P., “Development of a Java-based framework for aircraft preliminary design and optimization,” 2015. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2015-2651>.
- [14] R. D. Finck, “USAF Stability and Control DATCOM,” Technical Report AF33(616)-6460, F33615-76-C-3061, McDonnell Douglas Corporation, Douglas Aircraft Division, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, April 1978. Originally published October 1960. Revised April 1978. Project No. 8219, Task No. 821901.
- [15] Howe, D., *Basic Lift, Drag and Mass Representations*, John Wiley and Sons, Ltd, 2000, Chap. 6, pp. 139–164. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118903094.ch6>.
- [16] Sadraey, M. H., *Aircraft design: A systems engineering approach*, Aerospace Series, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118352700>, URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/9781118352700>.

- [17] Tariq, M., Maswood, A. I., Gajanayake, C. J., and Gupta, A. K., "Aircraft batteries: current trend towards more electric aircraft," *IET Electrical Systems in Transportation*, Vol. 7, No. 2, 2017, pp. 93–103. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-est.2016.0019>.
- [18] Kühnelt, H., Mastropierro, F., Zhang, N., Toghyani, S., and Krewer, U., "Are batteries fit for hybrid-electric regional aircraft?" *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 2526, No. 1, 2023, p. 012026. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2526/1/012026>, URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2526/1/012026>.
- [19] Gifford, S., "Powering the Skies: The Rise of Electric and Low-Carbon Aircraft," *Faraday Insights*, , No. 19, 2024. URL <https://faraday.ac.uk/insights/powering-the-skies/>, chief Economist, Faraday Institution.
- [20] Lombardo, T., "Inside Siemens' Record-Breaking Electric Aircraft Motor," *Engineering.com*, 2016. URL <https://www.engineering.com/story/inside-siemens-record-breaking-electric-aircraft-motor>.
- [21] Pastra, C. L., Hall, C., Cinar, G., Gladin, J., and Mavris, D. N., "Specific Power and Efficiency Projections of Electric Machines and Circuit Protection Exploration for Aircraft Applications," *2022 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference & Expo (ITEC)*, 2022, pp. 766–771. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITEC53557.2022.9813927>.
- [22] Hall, C., Pastra, C. L., Burrell, A., Gladin, J., and Mavris, D. N., "Projecting Power Converter Specific Power Through 2050 for Aerospace Applications," *2022 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference & Expo (ITEC)*, 2022, pp. 760–765. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITEC53557.2022.9813991>.
- [23] Chiara Massaro, M., Pramotton, S., Marocco, P., Monteverde, A. H. A., and Santarelli, M., "Optimal design of a hydrogen-powered fuel cell system for aircraft applications," *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol. 306, 2024, p. 118266. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118266>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0196890424002073>.
- [24] Aerospace Technology Institute – FlyZero, "Fuel Cells Roadmap Report," Tech. Rep. ZO-PPN-COM-0033, Aerospace Technology Institute, March 2022. URL <https://www.ati.org.uk/flyzero>, published by the Aerospace Technology Institute as part of the FlyZero project.
- [25] Link, A., and de Graaf, S., "Projection of Key Powertrain Component Figures of Merit for Overall Assessment of Electric Flight Scenarios," *ICAS 2024 Florence*, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Florence, Italy, 2024.
- [26] Hendricks, E. S., and Gray, J. S., "pyCycle: A Tool for Efficient Optimization of Gas Turbine Engine Cycles," *Aerospace*, Vol. 6, No. 87, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/aerospace6080087>.
- [27] Daggett, D. L., "Water Misting and Injection of Commercial Aircraft Engines to Reduce Airport NOx," NASA Technical Report CR-2004-212957, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, 2004.
- [28] Lin, C.-S., Van Dresar, N. T., and Hasan, M. M., "A pressure control analysis of cryogenic storage systems," Analex Corp. and NASA Lewis Research Center, AIAA, Conference Paper, 1991. AIAA PAPER 91-2405.
- [29] Drela, M., and Youngren, H., *XROTOR: Interactive Program for Design and Analysis of Propellers and Windmills*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2022. Available at <https://web.mit.edu/drela/Public/web/xrotor/>.
- [30] Lutze, F. H., "AOE 3104 Vehicle Performance," , 2018.
- [31] Hamilton, S., "Generalized Method of Propeller Performance Estimation 1961-1963," , 1963. URL <https://open.bu.edu/handle/2144/10454>.